

SOLAR WIND DEGRADATION OF THE LUNAR SURFACE SINCE THE PRE-NECTARIAN ERA.

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Introduction: Pre-Nectarian terrain, such as the most ancient impact basins, is an important record of the first ~13% of lunar history. It has had significantly longer to be worn down by space weathering and internal flux compared to later epochs, and is now among the most degraded. As many features from this era such as early impact basins are valuable for statistical analysis, it is necessary to constrain the rate at which surface degradation has occurred. Various estimates have been posited from both manual and automated inspections, though much emphasis has been placed on meteoritic flux and its role in diffusion (redistribution) downward of regolith. We investigate instead the role of solar wind on erosion (permanent loss) using a 1D semi-empirical model and reaffirm that while solar wind is not a major source of *erosion*, it may amplify the rate of *diffusion*.

Erosion, Diffusion & Degradation: We estimate $\approx 1.4m$ ($0.32nm/yr$) of net erosion and an associated diffusion rate of $\approx 2.1km$ over the last 4.5Ga. However, to contextualise this result, we must distinguish between “erosion” and “diffusion,” as various estimates have used the two interchangeably. *Erosion* refers to the amount permanently lost or displaced (e.g. to the exosphere or flung beyond the area), while *diffusion* is the localised dispersion of terrain, including fallback and infill. *Degradation* is the sum of these products. Without this distinction, it would imply that only $\approx 1.4m$ of terrain has been removed; alternatively, without erosion, all diffused terrain would stay localised. Pre-Nectarian basins show why both are necessary; the km-scale difference in altitude between ring fragments and infilled floors cannot be explained purely by permanent removal. Conversely, high-energy events involved in diffusion such as ballistic sedimentation and cosmic rays can strongly delocalise regolith; thus, both are necessary to fully account for the current state of the lunar surface. Proximity to the Sun and surface composition are the two most influential factors. The lithology of Mercury is comparable, but experiences much more intense solar wind, and thus yields a higher $11.3m$ ($2.5nm/yr$) over 4.5Ga. However, Ceres also yields a higher value of $1.97m$ ($0.43nm/yr$) despite being further from the Sun due to its ice-phyllsilicate mix. Even Neptune’s moon Triton yields $1.73m$ ($0.39nm/yr$) due to its icy shell. The Moon’s lower degradation rate can be attributed to less intense solar wind than at Mercury and a composition of higher binding energies than phyllsilicates and organic ices predominant further away. This might be a factor in the relative preservation of the oldest lunar basins

(*South Pole Aitken* $\approx 4.3Ga$) over Mercury (*Tolstoj* $\approx 3.85Ga$) or Ceres (*Kerwan* $\approx 1.3Ga$).

Previous Models of Erosion: Impact craters and basins are a common context for degradation studies since the progression can be measured by their structural breakdown. Fielder (1963) [1] suggested a very early rate of ‘extrinsic’ erosion of $1000nm/yr$, and that ‘intrinsic’ processes would predominate. This was challenged by Ross (1968) [2], who argued that both were necessary - not just impactors - to explain the removal of structures above 100m in diameter. Craddock & Howard (2000) [3] estimated a diffusion rate of $2 \times 10^{-7}mm/yr$, or 700m since the Imbrian by impactor flux alone. Starukhina (2003) [4] specifically modelled solar wind erosion as a Monte Carlo simulation, finding only $0.2nm/yr$ ($0.9m$ over 4.5Ga); this however only considered a monolithic target with a single H^+ ion flux; the distinction between “erosion” and “diffusion”, and between solar wind and impact flux, is shown by these studies to span several orders of magnitude. Fassett *et al* (2012) [5] found that the degradation of Mercury’s basins was far more extensive as a result of higher relaxation and proximity of solar wind allowing efficient burial and modification, which reaffirms the dual influences of surface composition and solar proximity; our results indicated a tenfold increase in solar erosion at Mercury. Fassett & Thomson (2014) [6] later utilised a diffusional model on 0.8-5km craters similar to Craddock & Howard (2000) [3], and found that after 3Ga, a 1km crater would reduce to only 52% of the original depth by impacts. However, this may be an overestimation as it assumes a constant rate of impact flux which is incongruous with size-frequency distributions. Povilaitis *et al* (2017) [7] also note that a larger structure requires significantly higher impact flux to remove all traces, which is more influential than its age, since weathering is nonlinear. Mahanti *et al* (2018) [8] provided one of the first automated methods for degraded <300m crater detection, finding

$$E(t)\dot{h}(t) = C(t) \left\{ \frac{\left(\rho(t) \left[(\epsilon(t)V_A(t))^{\frac{1}{2}} L(t)^{\frac{1}{2}} D(\theta(t), h(t)) \right]^{2\eta} (1 + \zeta(t))^2 \left(1 + \frac{h_r(t)}{L(t)} \right)^\alpha \right)^m}{\tau_c(t) \left[1 + T_{imp}(t) \right] - 1} \right\} \left(\frac{h(t)}{h_0(t)} \right)^{-\beta} \\ + m_r(t) \frac{\alpha Y_{eff}(t) k_p T(t) S_r(t)}{U_{eff}(t)} f(t) [N(t) S_n(t) D(\theta(t), h(t))] [V(t) S_v(t) D(\theta(t), h(t))] \\ \times \prod_{j \in \{ms, cx, wp\}} [1 + M_j(t)] [1 + T_{imp}(t)] [1 + \epsilon\eta(t)h(t)^r].$$

Equation 1 (above): 1D Solar Wind erosion model.

that traditional analyses are subjective on what constitutes ‘degradation’ – however, their model was trained on a manually curated dataset and assumed circular structure. These issues persist; Fairweather *et al* (2022) [9] only detected unambiguous degraded craters up to ~20km due to practical limits to visual analysis such as resolution even with automata.

1D Solar Wind Erosion Model:

Parameter	Definition	Values
$\rho(t)$	Solar Wind Density	5 cm^{-3}
$\epsilon(t)$	Energy Cascade Rate	$1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ Jkg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
$V_A(t)$	Alfven Velocity	50 kms^{-1}
$L(t)$	Outer Scale of Turbulence	$10^4 - 10^5 \text{ km}$
$\mu, \eta, C, \zeta, \alpha, m, \beta, k_B(t)$	Scaling constants (first approximations)	$0.05, 1.15, 1, 1.15, 1 - 2, 1 - 2, 0.5, 1.38 \times 10^{-23}$.
$D(\theta(t))$	Angle of the flux (loss cone modulation)	$0 - 180^\circ$. Weakest at 90° (magnetic mirror effect)
$h(t), h_0(t)$	Current & Initial Heights	Depends on topology.
$h_r(t)$	Characteristic roughness exponent	$5 - 30 \mu\text{m}$ (fine) 1mm (coarse)
τ_c	Critical material shear	For a mix of 80% plagioclase, 15% basalt, 5% pyroxene, 62.5MPa .
$T_{imp}(t)$	“Impulses” such as CMEs, solar flares etc	9.4×10^{-6} to 1.43×10^{-4}
m_r	Mass ejected by one solar wind atom	2.99×10^{-26} to 3.15×10^{-26}
αY_{eff}	Net yield, dependent on material strengths	$0.034 - 0.035$
U_{eff}	Binding energy, also depends on strength of composition.	$\approx 9.45 \times 10^4 \text{ J/m}^3$ for 80% plagioclase, 15% basalt, 5% pyroxene. Assume a grain size of 5mm microstructure.
$\mathcal{T}(t), \mathcal{N}(t), \mathcal{V}(t)$	Parker Temperature, Number Density and Velocity since 4.5Ga.	$\mathcal{T}: 1 - 6 \times 10^5 \text{ K}$ Modern value is $\sim 1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ K}$ and was 2-3x stronger 4.5Ga; estimate $3 - 4.5 \times 10^6 \text{ K}$. $\mathcal{N}: 50 - 100 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ $\mathcal{V}: 400 - 600 \text{ kms}^{-1}$
$S_T(t), S_N(t), S_V(t)$	Temperature, Number Density & Velocity evolution modifiers (since 4.5Ga)	$S_T: \approx 2 - 3 \text{ K}$ $S_N: \approx 3.5 - 3.88 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ $S_V: \approx 0.08 - 0.78 \text{ kms}^{-1}$
M_{ms}, M_{cx}, M_{wp}	Magnetospheric shielding, charge exchange and wave-particle interaction corrector terms.	$M_{ms}: \approx 0.67$ $M_{cx}: \approx 0.999$ $M_{wp}: \approx 0.9$ Assumes 96% H^+ , 3% He^+ and 1% HZE^+ and particle density of $3 \times 10^{4-5}$.

Table 1: Parametric values utilised.

In light of the issues reported by visual analyses, our model is purely mathematical and not based on any particular structure; it would be possible to define a topological function that describes the initial structure’s profile (e.g. a flat basin floor and rings) and integrate the flux over the entire domain. The first term represents shearing within the solar wind plasma, which despite being collisionless drives turbulent flow over long distances (Pinto *et al*, 2021) [10], whose influence weakens with depth (O’Brien & Byrne, 2022) [11]. The second introduces sputtering, i.e. atom-by-atom stripping from a coherent structure (e.g. grains), both within the solar wind kinetics and mechanical properties. The third holds correctors, such as flux spikes from solar magnetic activity (e.g. CMEs). Stochastic terms $\zeta(t)$ and $\epsilon\eta(t)$ modelled as Ornstein-Uhlenbeck processes acknowledge that some uncertainty is inevitable; our results may overestimate without ~15% stochasticity.

Results: This model yields $\approx 1.4\text{m}$ erosion over 4.5Ga, or $\approx 0.32\text{nm/yr}$. This is slightly higher than reported by other solar wind models such as Starukhina (2003) at 0.20nm/yr , which is likely due to multi-species solar wind and multi-materials in our model. This is lower than Mercury (2.5nm/yr), Ceres (0.43nm/yr) or Triton (0.39nm/yr), probably due to higher binding energy and lower solar flux. Solar wind also alters grain cohesion, boundaries and nanostructure, meaning erosion may enhance diffusion. The *diffusion length scale* defines the altitude that a structure dissipates down to in a given amount of time, as $L = \sqrt{E\kappa t}$, where E is the eroded amount (1.4), κ is the diffusivity constant ($\approx 10^{-3}$) and t is the time (4.5×10^9). Over 4.5Ga, the surface lowers by $\approx 2500\text{m}$; without erosion, this reduces to only $\approx 2100\text{m}$. The oldest impact basin is $t = 4.3\text{Ga}$, giving a practical maximum of $E = 1.35\text{m} \rightarrow L = 2.4\text{km}$. This would similarly justify the weak traces of basins on Mercury and Ceres, whose length scales of $\approx 3.4\text{km}$ and $\approx 3\text{km}$ respectively mean any structures below this have likely faded in 4.5Ga. Future research will address the challenges to the model posed by young, icy surfaces whose degradation may be ‘reversed’ by cryovolcanic and subsurface ocean replenishment. This model will be comprehensively expanded to capture the influence of cosmic rays, impact flux, endogeny and topology.

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